

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 103

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 103

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 103:0 <i>A Psalm</i> of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 103:1 לְדָוִד אֲבָרְכִי נַפְשִׁי אֶת־</p>
<p>Psa. 103:1 "Bless the LORD, O my soul, And all that is within me, <i>ble</i>ss His ^holy name. ² Bless the LORD, O my soul, And "forget none of His benefits; ³ Who "pardons all your iniquities, Who ^hheals all your diseases; ⁴ Who "redeems your life from the pit, Who ^bcrowns you with lovingkindness and compassion; ⁵ Who "satisfies your ¹years with good things, So <i>that</i> your youth is ^brenewed like the eagle.</p>	<p>יְהוָה וְכָל־קִרְבֵי אֶת־שֵׁם קְדֹשׁוֹ :² בְּרַכֵּי נַפְשִׁי אֶת־יְהוָה וְאֶל־תִּשְׁכַּחֵי כָל־גַּמּוּלָיו :³ הַסֵּלַח לְכָל־עֲוֹנוֹתֵי הָרָפָא לְכָל־תַּחֲלָאִיכִי :⁴ הַגּוֹאֵל מִשְׁחַת תַּיִכִי הַמְעַטְרֵכִי תְּסֹד וְרַחֲמִים :⁵ הַמְשַׁבֵּיעַ בְּטוֹב עַדְיָךְ תַּתְּחִישׁ כַּנְּשָׂר נְעוּרַיִכִי :⁶ עֹשֶׂה צְדָקוֹת יְהוָה וּמִשְׁפָּטִים לְכָל־עֹשִׂיקִים :⁷ יוֹדִיעַ דְּרָכָיו לַמַּשֶּׁה לְבָנָי יִשְׂרָאֵל עַל־לִוְתָיו :⁸ רַחֲמוֹ וַתִּנּוֹן יְהוָה אֶרֶץ אֲפִים וְרַב־תְּסֹד :⁹ לֹא־לִיגִצַח יָרִיב וְלֹא לְעוֹלָם יִטּוֹר :¹⁰ לֹא כַחֲטָאֵינוּ עָשָׂה לָנוּ וְלֹא כְעֹנֹתֵינוּ גָּמַל עָלֵינוּ :¹¹ כִּי כַגְּבוּהַ שָׁמַיִם עַל־הָאָרֶץ גָּבַר תְּסֹדוֹ עַל־יִרְאָיו :¹² בְּרַחֲקֵי מִזְרַח מִמַּעַרֵב הִרְחִיק מִמֶּנּוּ אֶת־בְּשָׁעֵינוּ :¹³ בְּרַחֲמֵי אָב עַל־בָּנִים רַחֲמֵי יְהוָה עַל־יִרְאָיו :¹⁴ כִּי־הוּא יִדְעַע יִצְרָנוּ זְכוֹר כִּי־עָפַר אֲנַחְנוּ :¹⁵ אֲנוֹשׁ כַּחֲצִיר יָמָיו כַּצִּיץ הַשָּׂדֶה כֵּן יִצְיָן :¹⁶ כִּי רֵוַח עָבְרָה־בּוֹ וַאֲיָנָנוּ וְלֹא־יִכְרְנוּ עוֹד מִקוֹמוֹ :¹⁷ וַתְּסֹד</p>
<p>Psa. 103:6 The LORD "performs ¹righteous deeds And judgments for all who are ^boppressed. ⁷ He "made known His ways to Moses, His ^bacts to the sons of Israel. ⁸ The LORD is "compassionate and gracious, ^bSlow to anger and abounding in lovingkindness. ⁹ He "will not always strive <i>with us</i>, Nor will He ^bkeep <i>His anger</i> forever. ¹⁰ He has "not dealt with us according to our sins,</p>	<p>וַתִּנּוֹן יְהוָה אֶרֶץ אֲפִים וְרַב־תְּסֹד :⁹ לֹא־לִיגִצַח יָרִיב וְלֹא לְעוֹלָם יִטּוֹר :¹⁰ לֹא כַחֲטָאֵינוּ עָשָׂה לָנוּ וְלֹא כְעֹנֹתֵינוּ גָּמַל עָלֵינוּ :¹¹ כִּי כַגְּבוּהַ שָׁמַיִם עַל־הָאָרֶץ גָּבַר תְּסֹדוֹ עַל־יִרְאָיו :¹² בְּרַחֲקֵי מִזְרַח מִמַּעַרֵב הִרְחִיק מִמֶּנּוּ אֶת־בְּשָׁעֵינוּ :¹³ בְּרַחֲמֵי אָב עַל־בָּנִים רַחֲמֵי יְהוָה עַל־יִרְאָיו :¹⁴ כִּי־הוּא יִדְעַע יִצְרָנוּ זְכוֹר כִּי־עָפַר אֲנַחְנוּ :¹⁵ אֲנוֹשׁ כַּחֲצִיר יָמָיו כַּצִּיץ הַשָּׂדֶה כֵּן יִצְיָן :¹⁶ כִּי רֵוַח עָבְרָה־בּוֹ וַאֲיָנָנוּ וְלֹא־יִכְרְנוּ עוֹד מִקוֹמוֹ :¹⁷ וַתְּסֹד</p>

Nor rewarded us according to our iniquities.

¹¹ For as high ^aas the heavens are above the earth,

So great is His lovingkindness toward those who ¹fear Him.

¹² As far as the east is from the west,
So far has He ^aremoved our transgressions from us.

¹³ Just ^aas a father has compassion on *his* children,

So the LORD has compassion on those who ¹fear Him.

¹⁴ For ^aHe Himself knows ¹our frame;

He ^bis mindful that we are *but* ^cdust.

Psa. 103:15 As for man, his days are ^alike grass;

As a ^bflower of the field, so he flourishes.

¹⁶ When the ^awind has passed over it, it is no more,

And its ^bplace acknowledges it no longer.

¹⁷ But the ^alovingkindness of the LORD is from everlasting to everlasting on those who ¹fear Him,

And His ²righteousness ^bto children's children,

¹⁸ To ^athose who keep His covenant
And remember His precepts to do them.

Psa. 103:19 The LORD has established His ^athrone in the heavens,
And His ^{1b}sovereignty rules over ²all.

²⁰ Bless the LORD, you ^aHis angels,
^bMighty in strength, who ^cperform His word,

יְהוָה יִמְעוֹלָם וְעַד-עוֹלָם עַל-
יִרְאָיו וְצִדְקָתוֹ לְבָנֵי בָנִים : ¹⁸
לְשִׁמְרֵי בְרִיתוֹ וּלְזִכְרֵי כְּפָרְיוֹ
לְעֲשׂוֹתָם : ¹⁹ יְהוָה בַּשָּׁמַיִם הַכִּיָּן
כִּסְאוֹ וּמִלְכוּתוֹ בְּכֹל מְשָׁלָה : ²⁰
בְּרַכּוּ יְהוָה מֵאֲחֵרֵי גִבּוֹרֵי כַח עֲשִׂי
דְּבָרוֹ לְשִׁמְעַע בְּקוֹל דְּבָרוֹ : ²¹ בְּרַכּוּ
יְהוָה כֹּל-צָבָאֵיו מִשָּׁרְתָיו עֲשִׂי
רְצוֹנָו : ²² בְּרַכּוּ יְהוָה אֶפְסֵי-מַעְשָׂיו
בְּכֹל-מְקוֹמוֹת מִמְשָׁלָתוֹ בְּרַכּוּ נַפְשֵׁי
אֶת-יְהוָה :

<p>^dObedying the voice of His word!</p> <p>²¹ Bless the LORD, all you ^aHis hosts, You ^bwho serve Him, doing His will.</p> <p>²² Bless the LORD, ^aall you works of His, In all places of His dominion; Bless the LORD, O my soul!</p>	
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References

Psalm 103:1

^aPs 104:1, 35

^bPs 33:21; 105:3; 145:21; Ezek 36:21; 39:7

Psalm 103:2

^aDeut 6:12; 8:11

Psalm 103:3

^aEx 34:7; Ps 86:5; 130:8; Is 43:25

^bEx 15:26; Ps 30:2; Jer 30:17

Psalm 103:4

^aPs 49:15

^bPs 5:12

Psalm 103:5

¹Or *desire*

^aPs 107:9; 145:16

^bIs 40:31

Psalm 103:6

¹Or *deeds of vindication*

^aPs 99:4; 146:7

^bPs 12:5

Psalm 103:7

^aEx 33:13; Ps 99:7; 147:19

^bPs 78:11; 106:22

Psalm 103:8

^aEx 34:6; Num 14:18; Neh 9:17; Ps 86:15; Jon 4:2; James 5:11

^bPs 145:8; Joel 2:13; Nah 1:3

Psalm 103:9

^aPs 30:5; Is 57:16

^bJer 3:5, 12; Mic 7:18

Psalm 103:10

^aEzra 9:13; Lam 3:22

Psalm 103:11

¹Or *revere*

^aPs 36:5; 57:10

Psalm 103:12

^{a2} Sam 12:13; Is 38:17; 43:25; Zech 3:9; Heb 9:26

Psalm 103:13

¹Or *revere*

^aMal 3:17

Psalm 103:14

¹I.e. what we are made of

^aIs 29:16

^bPs 78:39

^cGen 3:19; Eccl 12:7

Psalm 103:15

^aPs 90:5; Is 40:6; 1 Pet 1:24

^bJob 14:2; James 1:10, 11

Psalm 103:16

^aIs 40:7

^bJob 7:10; 8:18; 20:9

Psalm 103:17

¹Or *revere*

²I.e. faithfulness to His gracious promises

^aPs 25:6

^bEx 20:6; Deut 5:10; Ps 105:8

Psalm 103:18

^aDeut 7:9; Ps 25:10

Psalm 103:19

¹Or *kingdom*

²I.e. the universe

^aPs 11:4

^bPs 47:2, 8; Dan 4:17, 25

Psalm 103:20

^aPs 148:2

^bPs 29:1; 78:25

^cMatt 6:10

^dPs 91:11; Heb 1:14

Psalm 103:21

^{a1} Kin 22:19; Neh 9:6; Ps 148:2; Luke 2:13

^bPs 104:4

Psalm 103:22

^aPs 145:10

Targum

Psa. 103:1 Composed by David, spoken in prophecy. Bless, O my soul, the name of the LORD, and let all my viscera bless his holy name. ² Bless, O my soul, the name of the LORD, and do not forget all his nourishment, for he made breasts for your mother instead of insight. ³ Who forgives all your iniquities, who heals all your diseases. ⁴ Who redeems your life from Gehinnom, who crowned you with kindness and mercy. ⁵ Who satisfies the days of your old age with goodness, and in the age to come, your youth will be renewed like the eagle of the canopy. ⁶ The LORD does acts of righteousness, and judgments for all the oppressed. ⁷ He revealed his ways to Moses, his deeds to the children of Israel. ⁸ The LORD is merciful and compassionate; he loathes anger and does many deeds of goodness and truth. ⁹ He will not quarrel always, nor will he retain hostility forever. ¹⁰ He has not dealt with us according to our sins, nor has he repaid us according to our iniquities. ¹¹ For as high as the heavens are above the earth, so great is his goodness to those who fear him. ¹² As far as the east is from the west, thus far has he removed from us our transgressions. ¹³ As a father (abba) who loves the children, so the LORD loves those who fear him. ¹⁴ For he knows our evil impulse that makes us sin; in his presence it is remembered, for we are from dust. ¹⁵ The days of a son of man are like grass; like a blossom of the field, so will he bloom. ¹⁶ For a storm-wind has blown on him and he is no more; and he no longer is aware of his place. ¹⁷ But the favor of the LORD is upon those that fear him, from this age to the age to come; and his generosity is for the children of [their] children. ¹⁸ For those who keep his covenant, and for those who remember his commandments to do them. ¹⁹ The LORD has established his throne in the highest heavens; and his kingdom rules over all. ²⁰ Bless the name of the LORD, O his angels, who are mighty in power, who do his word, to obey the sound of his word. ²¹ Bless the name of the LORD, all his hosts, his ministers who do his will. ²² Bless the name of the LORD, all his works, his dominion is in every place. Bless, O my soul, the name of the LORD.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

King David thanked the LORD for His greatest gift – the soul. The soul allows humanity to become a reflection of the sacred heavens, a semblance of the Divine. People often ignore their souls and the true purpose of existence. Too often, the Divine fragment of the soul is overshadowed by the darkness of the flesh. The fundamental lesson of Judaism is to foster an awareness of the Divine soul and to teach humanity how to enhance and enrich the most precious possession so that it will become worthy of standing in the LORD's presence to praise Him.

Verse four

The Sefirah Chesed sends the LORD's lovingkindness to the souls in the grave to raise them to heaven. Through Chesed, the Divine part of the soul is brought back into the Lower Waters of Heaven.

Who redeems your life through Chesed with lovingkindness.

Verse eighteen

As in Psalm 102, an important spiritual lesson is that if a person wants their prayers heard and responded to, they have to live by the LORD's Laws.

To such who keep His covenant to fulfill them

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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